

pH biosensor based assay for SLC9B2 using HEK-293 SLC9B2 OE cells

PubChem ID: 1794821

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Assay description

pHluorins are pH-sensitive genetically encoded fluorescent sensors, that allow measurement of intracellular pH in living cells. In particular, pH-Axxam-Sensor (pHAxensor) is a chimera between a pH-insensitive Red fluorescent protein (RFP) and a pHluorin, pH-sensitive Green fluorescent protein (GFP). At acidic pH, pHluorin is quenched, whereas at physiological pH, pHluorin fluorescence increases.

SLC9B2 belongs to the Cation/Proton Antiporter (CPA) superfamily, and it couples inward transport of protons to mediate sodium efflux from the cells. Activation of SLC9B2 leads to pH changes that can be detected by the pH biosensor.

Figure 1. Principal of the pHAxensor assay. pHAxensor is a pH sensitive biosensor, a chimera between a pH-insensitive Red fluorescent protein (RFP) and a pH-sensitive Green fluorescent protein (GFP). pHAxensor shows high dynamic range for pH measurement in living cells and pKa around 7. The pH sensitivity in a full linear range is between 6.4-7.7. At acidic pH, GFP is quenched, whereas at physiological pH, GFP fluorescence increases.

Assay protocol

To develop a functional recombinant SLC9B2 cell-based assay, HEK-293 cells already expressing pHAxensor, were stably transfected with the SLC9B2 coding sequence. Mock control (transfected with the empty plasmid) was generated in parallel. Two rounds of limiting dilution led to the isolation of pure clones, the final clone was subjected to pharmacological characterization and tested to verify that the assay fulfils HTS quality criteria in terms of robustness and reproducibility.

Cell preparation

Cells were detached from 80% confluent flasks, transiently transfected with Superclomeleon biosensor expressing construct. Transfection was performed in suspension, using the Lipofectamine 2000 method following manufacturer's instruction. Cells were seeded at 20'000 cells/well in black-clear bottom poly-D-Lysine coated 384 well plate in complete medium and incubated 24 hours at 37°C, 5% CO₂.

pH biosensor assay

Medium was removed and cells were incubated 10 minutes at RT in 20 µL/well of Standard Tyrode's Buffer. Plates were analysed at Hamamatsu FDSS7000EX reader using a 472 nm excitation filter and a 542 nm emission filter.

To test pharmacology 20 µL/well of protons D/R (2X in Sodium free Buffer; 0.5% DMSO final concentration) to reach the final pH of 7.4 – 7.2 – 7 – 6.8 – 6.4 – 6.2 – 6 – 5.5 was online injected at the plate reader.

To test the effect of Phloretin as potential SLC9B2 inhibitor, a D/R of this compound up to 500 µM, serial dilution 1:3 (8 concentrations, DMSO only included) in Tyrode's standard buffer was online injected at Hamamatsu and fluorescence recorded. Then protons to reach a final pH of 6.2 were online injected in sodium free buffer and fluorescence recorded.

To assess robustness, reproducibility and amenability to high-throughput screening three 384-well plates were run consecutively using the following plate layout for one (Figure 2).

- Col 1 and 24 protons dose response curve
- Col 2 to 23 Protons EC₁₀₀ (final pH 6)
- Col 2 to 23 Neutral Control (0% Activity): +0.5% DMSO (final pH 7.4)

Data analysis

Hamamatsu FDSS7000EX measurements were analysed by using the Hamamatsu software (FDSS7000EX/μCELL software U8524-03A). Absolute Response (Relative Fluorescence unit, RFU) was obtained applying “Subtract Bias on Sample: n” (where n = Timepoint of compound injection). Data were then exported as Area Under the Curve (AUC). Mean and standard deviation of each replicate were calculated on the exported data with Excel software, then values were used to create sigmoidal dose-response curves (variable slope) and to calculate EC50/IC50 values with GraphPad PRISM software (Version 8).

Additional information

Target data

SLC	SLC9B2
Synonyms	Sodium/Hydrogen Exchanger-Like Domain-Containing Protein 2, NHA2
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 9 (Cation Proton antiporter 2)
UniProt ID	Q86UD5
RESOLUTE Cell ID	HEK-293/SLC9B2 K5.3 p3 (Axxam cell line)

Assay data

	Compound name (1)	Phloretin
	PubChem CID	4788
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma Aldrich, #P7912
	Mode of action	Inhibitor

	<p>Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)</p>	<p>IC₅₀ = 90 μM</p>
		<p>Z' factor calculated as</p> $RZ' = 1 - \frac{3 \cdot RSD(CR_p) + 3 \cdot RSD(SR_p)}{ (CR_p) - (SR_p) }$ <p>in single injection protocol</p>
		<p>Intraplate Variability calculated as</p> $\text{Variability Intraplate}_{CR} = \frac{SD(CR_p)}{ SR_p - CR_p } \times 100$ $\text{Variability Intraplate}_{SR} = \frac{SD(SR_p)}{ SR_p - CR_p } \times 100$ <p>in single injection protocol</p>
		<p>Interplate Variability calculated as</p> $\text{Variability Interplate}_{CR} = \frac{\overline{CR_p} - \text{mean}(\overline{CR_{p,d}})}{ \overline{CR_{p,d}} - \overline{SR_{p,d}} } \times 100$ $\text{Variability Interplate}_{SR} = \frac{\overline{SR_p} - \text{mean}(\overline{SR_{p,d}})}{ \overline{CR_{p,d}} - \overline{SR_{p,d}} } \times 100$ <p>in single injection protocol</p>

Discussion

The pH biosensor assay for SLC9B2 showed biosensor fluorescence quenching suggesting SLC9B2 mediated protons internalization. Phloretin showed inhibitory effect on the fluorescence quenching induced by cell acidification. The assay fulfils the HTS quality criteria.

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Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).